

ABOUT MUSIC CULTURE AND PIANO

Ermanova Dilafruz

Republic of Karakalpakstan.

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Abstract. *This article is about music culture and piano and its history.*

Key words: *music, culture, piano, education, grand piano.*

О МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ И ФОРТЕПИАНО

Аннотация. *Эта статья о музыкальной культуре и фортепиано и их истории.*

Ключевые слова: *музыка, культура, фортепиано, образование, рояль.*

In a number of countries, the educational process organized at school and outside of school, its forms and methods are undoubtedly attracting great interest. In many countries of the world, musical education of the young generation is of national importance and is an important means of personality formation. Music education of every country serves the social system of the people ideologically and politically.

The methodology of music education in the education of each nation is based on the didactic laws of pedagogy and the national musical culture, language and cultural traditions of this nation. At the same time, the structure, system (system) of music education and scientific-methodical achievements have a positive effect on the educational culture of other nations.

Raising a mentally and physically healthy generation in the development of our society is considered one of our most important tasks today. Because at the root of these thoughts, as always, are young people, the reason is that the education they receive today is not only for themselves, but also for the development of our country. is the most important foundation for Dear President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's clear opinion that "If you ask me what is bothering you, I will answer that it is the education and training of our children" is a clear proof of our opinion.

The role of music and art in the development of the society in which we live is incomparable. This is what strengthens our traditions that unite all nations and peoples. It is not an exaggeration to say that music can conquer any heart, plant the seeds of goodness in people's hearts and fight against other evils. At this point, it is self-evident that the art of music is incomparable and that it has great educational significance.

Musicologists, thinkers and scientists have long been attracted by the wide possibilities of music's influence on the human psyche. They tried to determine the characteristics of the art of music that affect the formation of people as individuals. Indeed, our great ancestors, who made a great contribution to the development of world science, deeply understood the role of music in the education of a perfect person, and researched its importance in the development of a person in their works and pedagogical views. great thinkers Al Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abdul Qadir Maroghi, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Mahmud Kashgari, Ahmad Yugnaki, Sadi Sherozi, Abdurrahman Jami, Kavkabi, Darveshali Changi, Kamil Khorazmi, Alisher Navoi, Zahriddin We can see that the information about music presented in a number of works of scholars such as Muhammad Babur is the most relevant and necessary source in the process of educating the young generation from a scientific, theoretical and educational point of view.

I think the best way to start music education is from the family. The reason is that interest in music depends on family environment. If the attitude towards art in the family is in a high spirit, high passion and respect, the child will develop a spontaneous interest and social-psychological environment.

It is known that a child brought up in a good family environment often has positive impressions of various life events, traditions, culture and art. Communication such as watching TV, watching concerts, watching theater and sharing one's impressions in the family together develops children's worldview and leads to understanding and artistic perception of the essence of literature, art and music reflecting life events.

Fortepiano, or as it was said earlier - pianoforte, can be literally translated as "low voice - high voice". This refers to the rich gamut of sounds that the piano can produce.

Nevertheless, this very complex instrument originated from the simplest monochord - a single-string box with musical intervals. Such sound boxes were also used in the cymbals and psalteries of the Torah period. In it, the musician moves his fingers along the intervals and clicks the strings.

Around 1000 AD, Guido d'Arezzo invented a portable base for the monochord, increasing the number of keys and strings. The tool was widely used in this form until the 16th century.

One of the most attractive instruments resulting from the improvement of the monochord is the clavichord. A piece made of copper appeared in it - a kolok. Its pressure caused the strings to vibrate, and as a result the sound of the instrument could be amplified or attenuated according to the musician's wishes.

Closest to the clavichord, the spinet is a four-octave, oblong instrument whose sound is obtained by plucking the strings.

By the middle of the 17th century, the harpsichord became popular. This instrument was larger than both the clavichord and the spinet, and usually had two keyboards. It looks like a grand piano. The sound is emitted from its strings with the help of small feathers.

Finally, in 1709, Bartolomeo Cristofori invented the system of hammers and used it to create a new instrument based on the harpsichord, the piano. The use of hammers made it possible to completely eliminate the squealing sound that usually destroys the sound of simpler instruments.

Beethoven was the first composer to put the piano into public use.

Fortepiano (Italian: forte - strong and piano - weak, slow) is a common name for grand pianos and pianos. At the beginning of the 18th century, B. Cristofori (Italy), J. Marius (France) and K.G. Invented by Schroeter (Germany). Later, the mechanism and shape of the piano were improved by I. A. Stein, I. A. Streicher (Austria), A. Beckers (London), S. Erard (Paris) and other masters. The sound is produced by striking the strings with wooden mallets covered with felt. It differs from the harpsichord and clavichord in its dynamic range (eg, the ability to move from a strong peg to a piano level) (hence the name). The first pieces for the piano were created by I. Haydn, V. A. Mozart, L. Beethoven and others. Due to its wide technical and expressive capabilities, the piano has become the main soloist and accompaniment instrument in European polyphonic music.

Piano music in Uzbekistan in the 1920-30s, starting with the Uzbek folk tunes reworked by V. Uspensky, B. Nadezhdin, later by G. Mushel, H. Izomov, B. Giyenko, Saifi Jalil, N. Zokirov,

in recent years by D. Saydaminova, R. Abdullayev, A. Nabiyev, M. Otajhonov, D. Omonullayeva and others, enriched with miniatures, sonatas and concerts, multi-part series. A. Lisovsky, N. Yablonovsky, Honored Artists of Uzbekistan O. Yusupova, A. Sharipova, Honored Teacher of Uzbekistan T. Popovich, winner of international competitions E. Mirkosimova, A. Sultanov, U. Polvanov and others contributed to the development of the art of piano performance in Uzbekistan. contributed.

The piano is the most complex musical instrument, excluding the organ. In general, its original name is pianoforte, which means "quiet-loud". This name comes from the fact that the piano can produce sounds of different pitches and strengths. The piano grew out of a very simple musical instrument called a monochord. A monochord is a monochord box with intervals on a scale reduced to itself. Around 1000 AD, Guido D'Aresso invented the sliding band for the monochord, added buttons and strings. The musical instrument he created was in use until the 16th century. Later it got another form - clavichord.

The sound of the clavichord was produced by the vibration of the strings under the influence of copper needles. The spinet is closely related to the above mentioned. It was an oblong musical instrument with a range of 4 octaves. Its strings were moved by mizrabs or buttons. A well-known musical instrument of the 18th century was called the harpsichord. It is larger than the clavichord and spinet and has two keyboards. It looks like a grand piano. Strings are set in motion with the help of small feathers. The real difference that separates these musical instruments from the piano is the movement of the hammers. It was invented by Bartolomeo Christopheri in 1709.

The hammers helped to get rid of the crunching sound that is inevitable in some simple musical instruments.

By the time of Mozart and Beethoven, the piano becomes a popular musical instrument.

Beethoven was the first composer to get the most out of the piano: his music requires a lower, deeper, more powerful piano sound.

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